

Patterns of Gender-Based Exploitative Behaviour as Perceived by Students in Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo, Nigeria

Oyetayo, M.O¹, Oyebanji, T.O²

^{1,2}Department of Educational Psychology and Counselling, Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

Gender based exploitive behavior has become a common phenomenon in Nigerian institutions of learning as it is being displayed by students and lectures. Gender based exploitive behavior (GBEB) can be described as any form of violation or discrimination either directly or indirectly against female which occur inform of rape, sexual harassment and intimidation

The research design adopted for the study is the descriptive survey, two hundred respondents were selected to participate in the study using the stratified sampling procedure. Three hypotheses were tested in the study, two of the hypotheses were accepted while one was rejected.

Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that There should be enlightenment campaign on the dangers of gender based exploitive behaviour with a view to reducing its prevalence and also that there should be stipulated punishment for offenders by relevant authority

KEYWORDS: behaviour, gender, patterns, violence

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INTRODUCTION

The Nigerian society has been plagued with several social vices recently, one of which is gender based violence which has become rampant in most tertiary institutions. Gender based exploitive behavior has become a common phenomenon in Nigerian institutions of learning as it is being displayed by students and lectures; due to its devastating effects, the issue requires urgent attention with a view to curbing the menace. The recognition of the widespread nature of gender based violence (GBV) in school settings is becoming an area of concern not least because of its infringement on the rights of the victims but also its impact on achieving the developmental goals related to equal access to education for boys and girls.

Violence against girls negatively impacts on their participation, retention and performance in schools. James (2024) observed that this problem is not only found in homes where the children are supposed to find security, but also in schools where they are under the custody of some of the very teachers who abuse them sexually and physically. In many developing countries parents are reluctant to send their daughters to school lest they risk violence, exploitation or defilement on their way to school or within the environment of the school. In many instances the journeys girls take to and from school expose them to assault either on foot or in vehicles. They become easy prey for men in private cars and are prone to other abuses such as injuries, violent robbery, rape and verbal abuse. In Kenya a study by FAWE titled "The Painful "Matatu Ride" revealed that many girls both in primary and secondary schools use the common public means of transport "Matatu" where the touts corrupt the girls with free rides "Sarees" and cash handouts as they enjoy latest music in such vehicles. This rides work against girls' education especially in towns as a significant number ends up pregnant and hence drop out of school or have their education interrupted. The problem is not only one of discrimination but a loss to the society as whole which is depriving itself of the potential of half its population especially at a time when countries need to compete in the world market.

Gender based exploitive behavior (GBEB) can be described as any form of violation or discrimination either directly or indirectly against female which occur inform of rape, sexual harassment and intimidation at school with attendant consequences like low self-esteem or confidence, unwanted pregnancy, abortion, mood changes, genital trauma and the list is on ending. The UN Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women (DEVAW) adopted by the UN General Assembly in 1993 has been influenced by CEDAW General Recommendation No. 19. It defines VAW as: "Any act of gender-based violence that results in,

or is likely to result in, physical, sexual or psychological harm or suffering to women, including threats of such acts, coercion or arbitrary deprivations of liberty, whether occurring in public or in private life." (Article 1) The declaration encompasses all forms of gender-based violence against women (physical, sexual and psychological), no matter in which context or setting they occur. Gender-based violence could come in different patterns which could be self-inflicted or imposed. It could be verbal, physical, psychological. Gender-based violence most occurred against female sex than male across the world. While men and boys can also be a victims of violence through physical or verbal attacks for transgressing predominant concepts of masculinity. But the main focus here is violence against women and girls in tertiary institutions because they are weak and vulnerable.

Statement of the problem

The growing rate of gender based exploitive behavior and its attendant effects such as poor academic performance, mood changes and the list is unending, indicates the need to carry out this research work and create awareness campaign among female students. Gender based violence is a serious violation of human rights and a complex problem all over the world. It is not specific to a particular country or region and women and men of all regions, religion or ethnicity can face discrimination and the consequent gender based violence. While it can affect both men and women, women are the group that is most affected. Gender Based Violence refer to sexual harassment, assault, verbal and physical abuse, psychological and economic violence women are specifically vulnerable to given the lack of power they possess in the society. The problem is compounded by harmful cultural practices like female genital mutilation, forced early marriages, forced prostitution, sexual harassment and sexual exploitation. Among the causes of GBV are poverty, traditional beliefs, some aspects of modernity and the socialization of girls and boys by the society makes victims accept it as norm. GBV limits girl's access, participation, retention in education and difficulties in finding jobs later. GBV as discussed by authors provides insights into its magnitude however; it is limited to secondary literature. This notwithstanding appropriate education provides an opportunity to learn about equality between men and women and non sexist education makes it possible to deal with traditional stereotypes concerning roles of women and men so as to fight prejudices and discrimination. This paper seeks to demonstrate the need for governments to reform their education systems to give girls and boys equal opportunities to participate and share benefits of education against general belief that GBV is more rampant in illiterate societies.

Rape is the classic case of crime where the victim is nearly always blamed. Only very young girls and very old women are not blamed for arousing the uncontrollable male lust. The onus is on women victims to convince the male world that she has been violated. For instance, Channels cable reported in April that there was an heavy increase in the number of rape cases reported to the Nigeria Police offices across the nation. The sudden increase in the cases was not far fetched because rapists co-habit with good Nigerians for weeks without going out during lockdown due to the outbreak of Coronavirus in year, 2020. In fact, aside rape other cases of violence were reported to have significantly increased since the lockdown began in the three most affected areas (Lagos State, FCT and Ogun State) on 30 March 2020. The Lagos State Domestic and Sexual Violence Response Team reported a three-fold increase in the number of telephone calls received through their hotlines in one month. In particular, service providers have reported sharp increases in cases of intimate partner violence and domestic violence. Data on reported incidents of these cases in Nigeria based on preliminary information from 24 states shows that in March 2020 alone, the total number of incidents reported were 346, while in the first part of April, incident reports spiked to 794, depicting a 56 per cent increase in just two weeks of lockdown. Some of these incidents of violence have tragically resulted in the death of victims, the rape of children, including incestual rape, and tenant-landlord assault. While federal and state governments put these measures in place to contain the spread of the virus, survivors of abuse have found themselves confined in their homes with abusers for weeks on end.

According to the World Health Organization multi-country study on violence against women, the lifetime and current prevalence of physical or sexual intimate partner exploitation among women ranged from 15 to 71% and 4 to 54%, respectively, and the prevalence of emotional violence ranged from 20 to 75%. In another study conducted by the World Health Organization, it was estimated that the lifetime prevalence of intimate partner violence among female youths aged 15-19 was 29.4 and 31.6% for ages 20-24. The highest prevalence of intimate partner violence was reported in the African region, particularly in Sub-Saharan Africa (65.64%). Evidence from Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) showed high rates of gender-based violence in educational institutions. Results from the Global Based School Survey (GBSS) revealed that the magnitude of current physical and sexual violence in five African countries ranged from 27- 50% and 9-33%, respectively. In research carried out in South Africa among adolescents aged 10-17 years, it was estimated that the lifetime prevalence (incident) of physical abuse was 56.3% (18.2%), emotional abuse 35.5% (12.1%), and sexual abuse 9% (5.3%). Researchers revealed the prevalence of attempted rape (18.7%), actual rape (23.4%), physically violent harassment (8.7%), verbal harassment (24.2%), and forced sexual initiation (11.2%) among female students in Wolaita Sodo University. In other researches, it was shown that the lifetime prevalence of rape was 11% among female secondary students in Arbamich

According to a research published by the "biomedcentral" journal in 2019, educational institutions in Africa, are high risk spaces for gender-based exploitation, violence perpetration and victimization. The reason for this is associated with a combination of different factors. Sexual harassment is unwelcome sexual behaviour that is offensive, humiliating or intimidating. It can be written,

verbal or physical, and can happen in person or online. Both men and women can be the victims of sexual harassment. When it happens at work, school, it may amount to sex discrimination.

Sexual harassment can include someone: touching, grabbing or making other physical contact with you without one's consent, making comments that has a sexual meaning, asking one for sex or sexual favours, leering and staring at one, displaying rude and offensive material so that one or others can see it making sexual gestures or suggestive body movements towards one, cracking sexual jokes and comments around or to you questioning one about one's sex life insulting one with sexual comments, making an obscene phone call and so on. While the definition of abuse is simple, the meaning and impact of abuse are very deep on the victim. Abuse is when one person purposefully hurts another, but that is a common occurrence in life and most of us are guilty of engaging in that from time to time. But what abuse really means is control. When a truly abusive situation exists, it's because one party is seeking to control the other through abuse. And while this might be an explanation of abuse, it's certainly no excuse. One person has no right to exercise control over another through abuse. Victims of abuse must know that the abuse is wrong and that the abuse is never their fault. Every person has the right to live an abuse-free life.

Research Questions

The following research questions are asked to guide the conduct of the study:

1. What are the patterns of gender-based exploitative behaviour?
2. Is there any difference in the patterns of gender based exploitative behaviour as perceived by respondents based on Gender?
3. Is there any difference in the patterns of gender based exploitative behaviour as perceived by respondents based on Religion?
4. Is there any difference in the patterns of gender based exploitative behaviour as perceived by respondents based on Age?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were generated for the study:

1. There is no significant difference in the patterns of gender based exploitative behaviour as perceived by respondents based on Gender
2. There is no significant difference in the patterns of gender based exploitative behaviour as perceived by respondents based on Religion
3. There is no significant difference in the patterns of gender based exploitative behaviour as perceived by respondents based on Age

Purpose of the study

The Purpose: of the study is to identify the Patterns of gender-based exploitative behavior as perceived by students in Adeyemi federal university of Education Ondo. The researcher considered variables Age, Gender and Religion as it affects the patterns of gender based exploitative behaviour.

Significance of the study

This research centres on finding the various patterns of gender based violence which has become endemic in the society, especially in tertiary institutions. The findings of this study could help in educating victims and vulnerables on the subject matter. This study will also draw the attention of the policy makers (as in Nigeria) on how policies could be initiated and implemented considering the traumatic effect of the problem. This research work could also help in proffering solutions and offering preventive measures with a view to curbing the problem of gender based violence.

Scope of the study

The study was limited to students in Adeyemi federal of Education Ondo, Nigeria, variables gender, religion and age were considered.

METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted for the study is the descriptive survey. The descriptive survey method entails the collection of data from representative sample of a population on which inference can be drawn on the entire population. Based on this, the method was considered appropriate for use in the study

Sample and Sampling Procedure

The target population for this study consists of all students in Adeyemi federal university of Education Ondo. However, because of constraints, two hundred respondents were selected using the stratified sampling procedure.

Psychometric Properties of the Instrument

The psychometric properties of the instrument lie in its validity and reliability.

Validity

An instrument is considered valid when it adequately measures what it, was designed to measure (Oyebanji, 2013). To ensure the validity of the research instrument, it was given to experts in the field of counselling with a view to establishing the content validity of the research instrument.

Reliability

Reliability entails the consistency of a research instrument, a research instrument is termed reliable if it measures what it is designed to measure consistently. To ascertain the reliability of the research instrument, the test-retest method of reliability was adopted; it was done by administering the test instrument to forty respondents at an interval of three (3) weeks, the two test results were then correlated using the Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation Coefficient formula and it yielded a coefficient of 0.76.

Instrumentation

The instrument used in collecting data is a researcher developed instrument tagged ‘Patterns of Gender Based Exploitative Behaviour Questionnaire’ The questionnaire has two sections (A, and B); section ‘A’ sought the demographic data of respondents while section ‘B’ contains items on the Patterns of Gender Based Exploitative Behaviour. The questionnaire was scored on a four-point Likert-type scale

Procedure for Data Collection

Data was collected by the researcher with the help of a research assistant, questionnaires were given directly to participants who were required to respond immediately and it was retrieved after completion.

Method of Data Analysis

In analyzing data collected for the study, both the descriptive and inferential statistics were adopted. Frequency counts and percentages were used to analyse the demographic section of the questionnaire while the t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Statistical Procedure was used to test the hypotheses. All hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Table 1: Demographic Data of Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	100	50.0
Female	100	50.0
Total	200	100
Religion	Frequency	Percentage (%)
ATR	02	1.0
Christianity	108	54.0
Islam	90	45.0
Total	200	100
Age	Frequency	Percentage(%)
16-20years	62	31
21-25years	104	52
26years and above	34	17
Total	200	100

The result in table 1 shows that on the distribution of respondents based on gender, there were equal representation of both genders (male & female), thus both males and females constituted 50% each of the total respondents.

On the distribution of respondents based on religion, the result shows that 2 respondents which represents 1.0% of the total respondents are of the African Traditional Religion, 108 respondents which represents 54.0% of the total respondents are Christians while 90 respondents representing 45.0% of the total respondents are of the Islamic religion.

Based on the distribution of respondents by Age, the result shows that respondents that are within the age range of 16-20 are 31% of the total respondents, respondents within the age range of 21-25 are 52% of the total respondent, while respondents that are 26years and above are 17% of the total respondents.

Table 2: Mean and Rank Order of Items on Patterns of Gender Based Exploitative Behaviour

The result in Table 2 indicates that, item 8 has the highest mean score of 3.17 thus it ranked 1st of all the items; this shows that physical violence is the highest pattern of Gender Basedl exploitative behaviour. However, item 10 which has to do with verbal abuse is the least pattern of gender Based exploitative behaviour, the item ranked last with a mean score of 2.70.

S/N	ITEMS	Mean	Rank
	Touching of sensitive parts of the opposite gender	2.99	3 rd
	Looking at the ooposite gender offensively	3.07	2 nd
	Use of sexually offensive words	2.96	4 th
	Cash for academic favour	2.80	6 th
	Favouring a specific gender above the other	2.79	7 th
	Verbal abuse	2.70	10 th
	Gender discrimination on award positions of responsibility	2.82	5 th
	Physical violence	3.17	1 st
	Sexual violence	2.78	8 th
	Emotional violence	2.72	9 th

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the Patterns of Gender Based Exploitative Behaviour as perceived by respondents based on Gender.

no significant difference

Table 3: Mean, Standard Deviation and t-value of Respondents on Patterns of Gender Based Exploitative Behaviour Based on Gender

Gender	N	x	SD	df	t-critic	t-cal
Male	100	85.32	6.1783	148	1.96	3.22
Female	100	85.32	8.2365			

The t-test result in table 3 shows that the calculated t-value of 3.22 is greater than the critical t-value of 1.96, based on this hypothesis 1 is rejected because a significant difference exists.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference on Patterns of Gender Based Exploitative Behaviour based on religion.

Table 4: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Result Comparing Responses on Patterns of Gender Based Exploitative Behaviour Based Religion

Source of variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	Critical f-value	Calculated f-ratio
Between Groups	3491.37	2	1745.685	3.00	2.86
Within Group	56875.28	147	11718.85s		
Total	60366.65	149			

ANOVA result in table 4 indicates that the calculated f-value of 2.86 is lesser than the critical f-ratio of 3.00, based no this result, hypothesis 2 is accepted because a significant difference does not exist.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference on Patterns of Gender Based Exploitative Behaviour based on Age

Table 5: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Result Comparing Responses on the Patterns of Gender Based Exploitative Behaviour by Respondents Based on Age

Source of variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	Critical f-value	Calculated f-ratio
Between Groups	2531.37	2	1265.69	3.00	1.46
Within Group	6687.28	147	3343.64		
Total	60366.65	149			

The result of the ten-item questionnaire on patterns of gender based exploitative behaviour indicates that physical abuse is the most ranked pattern of gender based exploitative behaviour, this is closely followed by item 2 which has to do with looking at the opposite gender offensively. This agrees with the findings of Ajewole, (2023) who find out that most women who experiences violence in their marriage are mostly abused physically. However, in the hypotheses testing, hypothesis 1 was rejected, it shows that a significant difference exists on the patterns of gender based exploitative behaviour as indicated by respondents based on gender. Conversely, a significant difference does not exist on the basis of religion and age of respondents.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this research work, the following recommendations were made:

1. There should be enlightenment campaign on the dangers of gender based exploitative behaviour with a view to reducing its prevalence
2. Stipulated punishment for offenders by relevant authority
3. There should be enlightenment campaign on the need for adopting good mode of dressing by ladies so as to reduce vulnerability

CONCLUSION

Based on this research work, gender based exploitative behaviour is known to be prevalent and comes in various patterns, a situation which is detrimental to the victims and the society at large based on the various effects it has on victims; such effects includes emotional, physical and esteem issues of affected individuals. It therefore becomes necessary to create awareness on the patterns and effects of gender based exploitative behaviour, this is with a view to reducing its occurrence. When there is enough awareness, potential victims will be able to act accordingly and perpetrators will also be brought to book; this will bring sanity to the society.

REFERENCES

- 1) Albert, K. E. (1995). "A Cry for Help". New Jersey: Princeton University Press.
- 2) Agha, U. A. (2003). Religious Ethics in a Permissive Society. Enugu: Saps Nig.
- 3) James, G.N. (2024). Causes of food insecurity in the midst of plenty. Contemporary issues in social sciences. 4(13)
- 4) Kpolovie, P. (2010). Advanced Research Methods. New Owerri: Springfield publishers.
- 5) Miltenberger, R. G. (2018): Behavior modification: Principles and procedures (4th ed.). Belmont, CA: Thomson Wadsworth.
- 6) Oyebanji, T.O (2013). Sources of National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) Pre-posting Anxiety as Expressed By Students of Tertiary Institutions in Ilorin Metropolis. International Journal of Research in Education, 11(1).
- 7) Slavin, R. E., 2016. Educational Psychology Theory into Practice. Englewood Cliffs. NJ Prentice-Hall.
- 8) Thorndike, E., (1975). The Educational Psychology: The Psychology of Learning. New York: Teachers College Press.
- 9) World Health Organisation (2019). Dangers of Female Genital Mutilation